

The distribution and status of flying squirrels in Karnataka and Goa

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Technical Report

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INTRODUCTION

Nocturnal mammals, on account of their elusive and cryptic habits, remain poorly known in many parts of the world, particularly in the tropics. Petauristinae (comprised of flying squirrels), one of the five families of gliding mammals, are an example, having received little scientific attention in the South Asia. While northeast India and north India together are inhabited by approximately 10 species of flying squirrels, only two species of flying squirrels occur in the Western Ghats: the small Travancore flying squirrel (*Petinomys fuscocapillus fuscocapillus*) and the large brown flying squirrel (*Petaurista philippensis*).

The small Travancore flying squirrel *Petinomys fuscocapillus fuscocapillus* is endemic to the forests of the Western Ghats (Kurup 1989). The species is rare (Xavier *et al* 1996), and is one of the lesser-known flying squirrels in India. *Petaurista philippensis* has a broader distribution and occurs in most of the forests of peninsular India (Prater 1971, Agarwal and Chakraborty 1979, Wilson and Reeder 1993). The conservation status of *P. f. fuscocapillus* has recently been assessed by the 2000 IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Hilton-Taylor 2000) as **Vulnerable** on the basis of its restricted distribution and the threats to its habitat. The Western Ghats is under increasing human pressure, and there has been a loss of over 25.6% of the total forest cover over the past 22 years (Jha *et al* 2000). Previous studies have shown that human disturbances gradually change the forest structure and composition and can have a deleterious effect on arboreal mammals (Sunderraj and Johnsingh 2001). Conversion of forested areas to plantations and other developmental activities that destroy or alter the habitat are believed to affect the population size and dispersal ability of the flying squirrels and result in the invasion of competitors, predators and pathogens (Weigl *et al* 1999).

There is very little information known on the two species of flying squirrels in South India, and our knowledge of their biology is restricted to basic natural history and distribution (for details refer Rajamani 2001). A recent study assessed the distribution of the two species in the Western Ghats of Tamil Nadu and Kerala (Rajamani 2001). *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered less frequently than *P. philippensis*, implying that it was the rarer of the two species, *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered only in Evergreen forests and Moist Deciduous forests, while *P. philippensis* was encountered in a variety of habitat types (Evergreen forests, Moist Deciduous forests, Shola forests, and Plantations). It was also encountered in a narrower altitude range

than was *P. philippensis*; *P. f. fuscocapillus* was only encountered up to 900m, while *P. philippensis* was encountered up to 2050m. However, though *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered only at a few sites, these were spread across the range of the Western Ghats of Kerala and Tamil Nadu, the southern most site where it was reported to occur being Shendurny Wildlife Sanctuary, and the northernmost being Aralam Wildlife Sanctuary. There exist no formal or published records of the species from the forests of Karnataka or Goa. It is reasoned from the results of the previous survey that there was a high probability of the species occurring in Karnataka, as it was reported in the forests of Kerala close to the Karnataka border. The forests of Karnataka have been described as being perhaps the most productive and least overexploited region with large tracts of pristine lowland and highland forests in the entire Western Ghats (Hussain *et al* 1999). Hussain *et al* (1999) have also highlighted the paucity of research on mammals in Karnataka, and have commented on the need for information. In the light of the above arguments this present study was initiated to document the distribution of both species of flying squirrels in the Western Ghats of Karnataka.

STUDY SITE

Field work was conducted over a period of three months between January and April 2002. 20 sites were surveyed in the Western Ghats of Karnataka and Goa, of which 18 sites were in Karnataka, and two were in Goa. Of the sites sampled 13 were protected areas (Sanctuaries and National Parks), while seven were non-protected areas (Reserve Forests) (Details of effort in Table A1). Evergreen forest, moist deciduous and dry deciduous forests were sampled at all the sites.

Due to time constraints and the vastness of the area involved, surveys were conducted in certain representative areas of the Western Ghats of Karnataka and Goa. The following forest areas were surveyed:

Karnataka: Mysore, Coorg, Belgaum, Kanara, Shimoga and Bellary Circles.

Goa: Panaji Circle (South Goa and North Goa divisions).

METHODS

DATA COLLECTION

Spotlighting

Existing trails were walked at all the sites. Trails were walked through all hours of the night; however, sampling effort was primarily focused between 1800 and 0100 hrs. In a previous survey (Rajamani 2001) activity of flying squirrels was seen to decline after 2330 hrs, and it was believed that best results would be obtained in the first half of the night. A spotlight connected to a 12 volt battery and flashlights powered by cells were used to locate the animals. Once eye shine was spotted, more light was used and the animal was identified with the help of 8X40 binoculars. All animals were identified to species, and when the sighted animal was identified as a flying squirrel, the following variables were recorded: time, height of animal on tree, substrate animal was on (trunk/branch), diameter of branch, behavior (feeding, grooming, gliding, resting, etc) The altitude and GPS locations of all sites surveyed were recorded.

Vegetation characteristics

All trees on which flying squirrels were located were marked and a plot of radius 11.3 m (James and Shugart 1970) was laid around these trees. Along trails where no flying squirrels were seen, vegetation plots were laid to the left and right of the trail around randomly selected trees. Plots laid around trees that flying squirrels were seen on are henceforth referred to as "sighting" plots and plots laid around random trees are denoted as "non-sighting" plots. The trees around which the plot was laid (both in sighting or non-sighting plots) are referred to as "centre" trees. A number of habitat parameters were recorded in each plot to characterize height of the tree the squirrel was on, and the height of the surrounding forest stand. The following variables were measured in each plot: the height and girth (at breast height - 1.3 m above the ground) of the centre tree, the phenological status of the trees, the number of hollows on the tree, the canopy cover (measured with a densitometer), and the canopy contiguity of the tree to the surrounding trees (measured by the number of trees that overlapped the canopy of the centre tree). The girths and heights of all the other trees in the plot were recorded to determine stand characteristics.

Nest plots

Plots were laid in Nagarhole National Park to investigate the utilisation of trees for nesting purposes. 50 x 50 m plots were laid at random along roads. The height, girth, and category of each tree in this plot was recorded, and each tree was searched for the presence of hollows.

When hollows were located, a trained field assistant climbed the tree to investigate if the hollow was occupied by a flying squirrel. All hollows (both occupied and unoccupied) were characterized, and the following variables were recorded: cavity shape, length, width, if the cavity was created artificially (created by birds) or naturally (limb fall), diameter at nest height, height of cavity on the tree, and distance to nearest limb. Trees that the hollows were on were also characterized, and the following parameters were recorded: Girth at breast height, height, phenology, canopy contiguity to nearest trees, and the distance of the tree to nearest road or trail. The presence or absence of ferns and the cover in height intervals of 5m in a radius of 5m around the tree were recorded. The life stage category of the tree was recorded in predetermined classes. The altitude, GPS location, topography and slope of the plot were also recorded.

Questionnaire

In addition to field surveys, a questionnaire (Appendix 2) was prepared to gather secondary information regarding the presence and awareness of the two species of flying squirrels at every site. Information on the natural history of the species was collected and an attempt was made to assess the threats to the two species. Information about other nocturnal mammals and arboreal herbivores was also collected whenever possible.

DATA ANALYSIS

The encounter rate was calculated as the number of flying squirrels sighted per kilometer of walk. This was the unit of occurrence of flying squirrels that was used for analysis. The encounter rates of the two species of flying squirrels were assessed with respect to habitat types and habitat characteristics. The statistical package SPSS (Norusis 1990) was used for most of the analysis. Mann-Whitney U tests (Sokal and Rolf 1990) were used to analyze the encounter of flying squirrels with respect to habitat and to determine if the occurrence of flying squirrels varied across vegetation categories, and if the occurrence of the two species of flying squirrels differed within a vegetation category.

Mann Whitney U tests were used to determine if any specific habitat characteristics were different in the habitats where flying squirrels occurred and where they did not. I also tested to see if habitat characteristics associated with the occurrence of the two species were different from each other.

Principal component analysis was used to analyse the pattern of occurrence of flying squirrels taking all habitat parameters into account. This analysis was used to determine if forest areas where flying squirrels were sighted were different from areas where no flying squirrels were sighted. The software package SAS was used for this purpose.

RESULTS

GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION

Field work was conducted over a period of two months between January and March 2002, and one additional week was sampled in April 2002 to cover a stretch of forest that had previously not been included.

20 sites were surveyed in the Western Ghats of Karnataka and Goa, of which 18 sites were in Karnataka, and two were in Goa. Of the sites sampled 13 were Protected Areas (Sanctuaries and National Parks), while seven were Non Protected Areas (Reserve Forests) (Details of effort in Table 1).

A total of 152 flying squirrels were sighted during the survey. The Travancore flying squirrel was sighted on 5 occasions while the Indian Giant flying squirrel was sighted on 147 occasions.

P. f. fuscocapillus was encountered at four sites, Pushpagiri Wildlife Sanctuary, Talacauveri Wildlife Sanctuary, Balehalli Reserve Forest and Mookambika Wildlife Sanctuary. The encounter rate of the species was highest at Hamiyala, at the border of Pushpagiri Wildlife Sanctuary (Encounter rate: 0.8 squirrels /km, n=1) followed by Talacauveri Wildlife Sanctuary (Encounter rate: 0.5 squirrels/km, n=1) (Map 1).

The Indian Giant flying squirrel was encountered along 31 walks in a total of 17 sites. The encounter rate was highest at Bhadra Wildlife Sanctuary (7.5 squirrels/km \pm 1, n=2), followed by Nagarhole National Park (3.37 squirrels/km \pm 1.16, n=6), Someshwara Wildlife Sanctuary (3.5 squirrels/km, n=1), *Kans* around Sorab (2.66 squirrels/km \pm 0.66, n=2), and Sharavathi Wildlife Sanctuary (2.19 squirrels/km \pm 0.24, n=3) (Map 1).

FOREST TYPES AND FLYING SQUIRRELS

A total of 113.35 km over 40 walks was sampled in Evergreen, Moist deciduous and Dry deciduous forests. Evergreen forests were most intensively sampled (n = 26, total km sampled = 81.9), followed by Moist deciduous forests (n = 12, total km = 24.75) and Dry deciduous forests (n= 2, total km = 4.7) (details of walks per site and effort in Appendix I).

Table 1: Encounter rates (# squirrels/km) of flying squirrels across sites and forest types.

<i>S.no.</i>	<i>Site</i>	<i>Forest type</i>	<i>Travancore flying squirrel</i>	<i>Indian Giant flying squirrel</i>
			<i>Encounter Rate</i>	<i>Encounter Rate</i>
1	Biligiri Rangaswamy Temple WLS	MDF, EG	-	0.91 ± 0.41
2	Nagarhole NP	MDF, DDF	-	3.32 ± 1.16
3	Brahmagiri WLS	EG	-	0.35 ± 0.26
4	Bhadra WLS	MDF	-	7.5 ± 1
5	Kudremukh NP	EG	-	0.58 ± 0.30
6	Sharavathi WLS	EG	-	2.19 ± 0.24
7	Anshi NP	EG	-	0
8	Bhagwan Mahaveer WLS	MDF	-	0.26 ± 0.07
9	Cotigaon WLS	EG	-	0.28 ± 0.28
10	Sorab	EG	-	0.26 ± 0.66
11	Talacauveri WLS	EG	0.5	2
12	Pushpagiri WLS	EG	0.8	1.6
13	Kemmangundi	EG	-	0.83
14	Someshwara WLS	EG	-	3.5
15	Balehalli	EG	0.4	1.2
16	Agumbe	EG	-	0.33
17	Mookambika WLS	EG	0.173	1.39
18	Haliyal	EG	-	0
19	Malemane	EG	-	0.5
20	Yana	EG	-	0

All locations of the Travancore flying squirrel were by direct sighting, while the Indian Giant flying squirrel was located by call on 27 occasions and by direct sighting on 120 occasions. All five sightings of *P. f. fuscocapillus* were in Evergreen forests, while *P. philippensis* was sighted in Evergreen, Moist deciduous and Dry deciduous forests. The proportion of *P. philippensis* detected by calls and sighting were significantly different in Evergreen and Moist deciduous forests ($df=1$, $\chi^2 = 5.9438$, $0.01 < p < 0.05$), with a greater proportion of flying squirrels being detected by calls in Evergreen forests than in Moist deciduous forests (Table 2).

The encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* in Evergreen forests was 0.072 squirrels/km (± 0.03 S.E.). The encounter rate of *P. philippensis* was highest in Moist deciduous forests (3.086 squirrels/km ± 0.922 S.E., $n=26$) followed by Evergreen forests (1.04 squirrels/km ± 0.20 S.E., $n=12$) (Fig. 1). However, the encounter rate of *P. philippensis* was not significantly different between Evergreen and Moist deciduous forests (Mann-Whitney U Test; $n_1 = 26$, $n_2 = 12$, $z = -1.645$, $p > 0.05$), Evergreen and Dry deciduous forests (Mann-Whitney U Test; $n_1 = 26$, $n_2 = 2$, $z = -.180$, $p > 0.05$), or moist and dry deciduous forests (Mann-Whitney U Test; $n_1 = 12$, $n_2 = 2$, $z = -.366$, $p > 0.05$).

Fig. 1: Encounter rates of the two species of flying squirrels across forest types.

NEST USE AND CHARACTERISTICS

Nine nests of *P. philippensis* were located in Nagarhole National Park during the study. Four of these nests were located by asking local inhabitants of the location of the nests and the rest were located while laying exploratory nest plots.

An average of 4.8 hollows (± 1.2 S.E.) was detected in each nest plot. Only three of the five plots had hollows occupied by flying squirrels. In each occupied plot, an average of 1.2 hollows (± 0.58 S.E.) was occupied by the Indian Giant flying squirrel (Table 2).

Examining the plots, it was observed that the number of hollows present in the plot did not correlate with the density of trees in the plot (Kendall's $\tau = 0.105$, $p > 0.05$). The number of hollows being used did not correlate with the total number of hollows present (Kendall's $\tau = 0.22$, $p > 0.05$), nor did it correlate with the density of trees (Kendall's $\tau = 0.108$, $p > 0.05$). However, it was seen that the distribution of trees in different girth classes between the plots where nest hollows were not located and between where 3 nest hollows were located was significantly different ($\chi^2 = 1068.075$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.00$). The result implied that there were more trees in the lower girth classes (girth class 0.3 - 1.0 m) where no flying squirrel nests were located, while the plot where 3 nests were located had most trees in the girth class 1.0 - 2.0 m and above. There was no difference in tree densities between the plots where nests were located ($\chi^2 = .7088$, $df = 2$, $p > 0.05$).

Table 2: Characteristics of nest plots.

	<i>Density (trees/ha)</i>	<i>Stand Height (m)</i>	<i>Basal area/ ha</i>	<i>Density hollows (ha⁻¹)</i>	<i>Density used hollows (ha⁻¹)</i>
Plot 1	452	13.42 (0.5)	0.579	20	0
Plot 2	128	21.66 (1.1)	0.296	8	4
Plot 3	100	18.2 (0.5)	0.180	36	8
Plot 4	92	19.30 (1.3)	0.149	12	0
Plot 5	112	19.21 (1.3)	0.233	20	12

75% of the nest hollows detected were round in shape, and 25 % were longitudinal. 63% of these hollows were natural hollows, while the rest were probably made by other hollow dwelling vertebrates (woodpeckers, etc). Most nests (74 %) were oriented towards the Southwest (Fig. 5.2). Flying squirrels were flushed out of their hollows when trees cavities were searched to determine occupancy. Of all the occupied hollows (n=11) examined nine had flying squirrels, and one hollow was occupied by a bat colony, and one other by bees. Flying squirrels once flushed glided away as soon as possible,

possibly in search of other tree cavities in which to seek refuge. On 2 occasions, flying squirrels glided directly to a tree with a cavity into which

Table 3: Nest tree and cavity characteristics.

<i>Characteristics</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Gbh of nest tree (m)	2.65 (0.22)
Height of nest tree (m)	25.75 (1.27)
Number of hollows	2.25 (0.49)
Diameter at nest height (m)	0.87 (0.09)
Height of the nest (m)	18.42 (1.79)
Length of cavity (cm)	38.4 (21.37)
Width of cavity (cm)	13.2 (2.76)

Figure 2: Orientation of nest cavities.

they entered. On 3 occasions, the cavities they glided to were occupied by other flying squirrels, and on all three occasions the intruding flying squirrels were chased away by the residents, often with aggressive displays. This knowledge of tree hollows in the surrounding area indicates that flying squirrels probably have an accurate map of their immediate surroundings and are aware of the availability of resources. The close spacing of flying squirrels and the presence of up to 3 nesting individuals within 0.25 ha calls for an investigation into the social system of flying squirrels.

HABITAT CHARACTERISTICS AND FLYING SQUIRREL OCCURRENCE

Since the Travancore flying squirrel was seen on too few occasions, the data collected around sighting plots of this species was not included for habitat analysis. Vegetation plots in dry deciduous forests were not used for habitat association analysis as there was insufficient sampling in this habitat type. This analysis details the habitat characteristics associated with the occurrence of the large brown flying squirrels in evergreen and moist deciduous forests.

Habitat characteristics were examined in both sighting and non-sighting plots to offer a clear picture of the specific habitat characteristics associated with the occurrence of flying squirrels. Evergreen and Deciduous forests were analyzed separately as the habitat features in these forests were too different to allow them to be pooled together.

In evergreen forests, non sighting plots were different from sighting plots with respect to center tree height ($Z = -3.062$, $p = 0.002$), centre tree girth ($Z = -2.342$, $p=0.019$) and canopy contiguity ($Z = -2.145$, $p = 0.032$). The center tree in sighting plots were taller and of larger girth than center trees in plots where flying squirrels were not seen (Table 1). Canopy contiguity of non-sighting trees was less than trees on which squirrels were sighted (Table 1).

In moist deciduous forests, sighting plots differed from non sighting plots with respect to average stand height ($Z= -3.201$, $p=0.001$), centre tree height ($Z=-4.077$, $p=0.000$) and girth ($Z= -3.271$, $p=0.000$), and density of the stand ($Z=-4.00$, $p=0.00$) (Table 2). As was seen in evergreen forests, average stand height, and center tree height and girth were greater for sighting plots. Canopy contiguity of the center tree did not differ significantly ($p>0.05$), though the canopy contiguity of the center tree in sighting plots was lower than that of non-sighting plots. Both these figures were similar to the canopy contiguity seen for sighting plots in evergreen forest (Tables 1 and 2).

The stand densities for sighting and non-sighting plots were significantly different in Moist deciduous forests but not in evergreen forests. Sighting plots had a lower stand density in Moist deciduous forests but no such trend was observed in evergreen forests. Examining the basal area of the stands there was no difference between sighting and non sighting plots in either forest type. The girth class distribution of trees was examined

to provide a better picture of the stand. A trend similar to the stand density was revealed and the distribution was significantly different in Moist deciduous forests though not in evergreen forests.

Table 4: Habitat characteristics in sighting and non-sighting plots: Evergreen forest

(Analysis with Mann-Whitney U tests, Z and p values displayed below)

<i>Habitat parameter</i>	<i>Sighting plots</i>	<i>Non sighting plots</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>P</i>
<i>Tree Density</i>				
<i>Average stand height</i>				
<i>Centre tree girth</i>				
<i>Centre tree height</i>				
<i>Basal area</i>				
<i># of hollows</i>				
<i>Canopy Contiguity</i>				

* significant at $p < 0.001$

** significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 5: Habitat characteristics in sighting and non-sighting plots: Moist deciduous forest (Analysis with Mann-Whitney U tests, Z and p values displayed)

<i>Habitat parameter</i>	<i>Sighting</i>	<i>Non sighting</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>P</i>
<i>Tree Density</i>				
<i>Average stand height</i>				
<i>Centre tree girth</i>				
<i>Centre tree height</i>				
<i>Basal area</i>				
<i># of hollows</i>				
<i>Canopy Contiguity</i>				

* significant at $p < 0.001$

** significant at $p < 0.05$

In Evergreen forests sighting plots the distribution of trees across different girth classes did not vary from non sighting plots ($\chi^2 = 5.54$, $df=4$, $p>0.05$). However, in Moist deciduous forests the girth class distribution in sighting plots varied significantly from non sighting plots ($\chi^2=13.73$, $df=3$, $p<0.001$).

In moist deciduous forests stands where flying squirrels were seen had a greater proportion of trees in the larger girth classes (2-4 m girth at breast height) while stands where flying squirrels were not seen seemed to have a greater proportion of smaller trees (in girth classes 0.3-1m gbh) (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Girth class percentage distribution of trees in sighting and non-sighting plots in Moist deciduous forests

(Girth classes: 1= 0.3-1m gbh, 2=1-2m gbh, 3=2-3m gbh, 4=3-4m gbh, 5= > 4m gbh)

HABITAT CHARACTERISTICS AND DISTRIBUTION

A principal component analysis was performed in order to explain the interactions between all the habitat variables simultaneously. The principal component analysis of habitat characteristics was pooled for the two major habitat types analyzed: moist deciduous forest and evergreen forest. The first three principal components explained 63 % of the variation in the data. The principal components showed significant variation between the sighting and non sighting plots on the first axis but not on the second.

The Principal components analysis of 9 character variables measured in 99 plots yielded four principal components with eigenvalues > 0.5 , and collectively accounted for 74 % of the variation in the original data. The first principal component was largely a height component, with high positive loadings for the height and the girth of the tree as well as the height of the stand. The second principal component was more of a stand structure component, with positive loadings for the number of hollows on the centre tree and the basal area of the stand. The third component was a vegetative component, contrasting phenology and canopy contiguity. Where the canopy was contiguous, there were lower phenology scores.

Evergreen forests

When the principal component analyses were carried out separately for the two habitats, the results were similar. The first component for evergreen forests was slightly different from the overall result, with the number of hollows replacing the stand height in this component. The second principal component comprised of stand density, canopy contiguity and the height of the stand. The third principal component comprised of many variables, and consisted of plots that had high density, high basal area, high number of hollows, and a greater perpendicular distance to sighting. This violates the assumption that perpendicular distance affects visibility. There was no significant difference along PC2 (t test, $t = 1.36$, $p > 0.05$) and only a difference along PC1 (t-test, $t = -3.07$, $p < 0.003$). PC1 was driven by the presence of large tall trees with a large / good number of hollows.

Taken together these variables define a habitat type that flying squirrels inhabit: flying squirrels seem to occur in tall mature stands with a good number of hollows, and good canopy connectivity.

Sighting and non-sighting plots in evergreen forests were plotted along the first two principal components axes as these were the 2 components that contributed most to the results (Fig. 5). Sighting and non-sighting plots were separated to a large extent; however, there seems to be an overlap of plots in certain regions of the graph. Plots were numbered according to the sites surveyed in order to obtain a clearer picture of the results (Fig. 6). When the specific plots that overlapped were examined, the distribution along the 2 axes became clear. Certain non-sighting plots (n1, n2, n3, n4, n5) seem to share similar characteristics with sighting plots. Plots n1 and n2 were located in BRT

Wildlife Sanctuary, in an evergreen forest with reports of high levels of hunting and poaching (local tribal communities, pers. comm.). A trap for deer (with a dead sambar *Cervus unicolor*) was found within a 1km radius of the surveyed site, and local residents reported that flying squirrels were hunted for both medicinal and meat purposes. Though these plots were located in relatively intact forest stands, hunting and poaching have affected animal populations.

The sighting plots (s6, s26, s17, s14, s13, s20, and s22) which seem to overlap with the non-sighting plots in the middle of the graph were sites (Sitanadi, Agumbe, Mookambika WLS, Kemmangundi, Megani) with a lot of habitat disturbance. A lot of sites were disturbed evergreen habitats where local communities logged adjoining forest regions. Logging and interference on a small scale alters the forest structure, and as a result these areas degrade sufficiently to resemble 'typical' non-sighting plots with lower stand height, fewer hollows and lower stand density. The sighting plots at the left extreme of the graph (s29, s27, s4) showed a similar trend, and were again sites with considerable habitat degradation. These sites were at the outskirts of human settlements. However, local human population densities were low and the practice of hunting was not very prevalent. The reason that squirrel populations were still found at these sites despite the disturbance to the habitat was low hunting and poaching pressure.

Moist Deciduous forests

When a principal component analysis was performed for moist deciduous forests, the results were similar to the results obtained when both the habitat types were pooled. The first principal component was driven by the height of the stand and the height and girth of the centre tree. The second principal component was affected by the density of the stand, the basal area and canopy contiguity. Principal component 1 was largely driven by structural characteristics and indicated the maturity of the stand, while the second principal component possibly indicated the connectivity of the stand, and both the branch and trunk cover of the stand as indicated by canopy contiguity and basal areas. Sighting and non-sighting plots were plotted along the first two principal component axes and were seen to be clearly separated. The point *n* towards the top right end of the plot was an outlier, as it was more similar in characteristics to the sighting plots than to the non sighting plots. However, much hunting has been reported in the adjoining areas and this is a possible reason for not sighting flying squirrels.

Figure 5: Principal component analysis of sighting and non-sighting plots in Evergreen forests (plots numbered).

Figure 6: Principal component analysis of sighting and non-sighting plots in Moist Deciduous forests.

CONCLUSION

The Indian giant flying squirrel was found across most of the sites surveyed in Karnataka, while the smaller Travancore flying squirrel was found to occur only north through the forests of mid Karnataka. While the Indian giant flying squirrel was sighted in both Karnataka and Goa, this survey recorded the presence of the Travancore flying squirrel only in the state of Karnataka. The Travancore flying squirrel was seen at sites at the border of Kerala, and in a total of four locations in Karnataka. However, since the northernmost forests that this species was sighted in are contiguous with the forests in North Karnataka leading into Goa, and it is likely that the Travancore flying squirrel occurs in Goa. Intensive studies are required the forests of North Karnataka and Goa before the presence of the species in this region can be completely ruled out.

An additional point to note is that residents and naturalists (pers. obs.) in Goa are familiar with the Travancore flying squirrel and can identify descriptions of the species reasonably accurately. Previous studies have thought the Travancore flying squirrel to be restricted in distribution to southern Kerala, and this is the first study to intensively explore and map the distribution of this species outside this region. Many mammal species have been understudied in India, and we do not have complete distribution records of many cryptic and nocturnal species. The brown palm civet, *Paradoxurus jerdonii*, was one of these, and this survey also resulted in records of this carnivore in Northern Karnataka and Goa (Rajamani et al 2002). The distribution of the lion-tailed macaque was also believed to be restricted to Tamil Nadu and Kerala (Krishnan 1972, Roonwal and Mohnot 1977), and it was believed that the evergreen forests of Karnataka were unsuitable for supporting viable populations of this rainforest specialist. Karanth (1985) disproved this in a survey of lion-tailed macaque populations in Karnataka, and found the species to be distributed north to the forests in Sirsi Forest Division. It is likely that many species have been described as restricted to the southern Western Ghats purely due to the lack of research in the northern half of the mountain range. Though Mookambika WLS was the northernmost point where the Travancore flying squirrel was sighted, it is likely that this species too will occur into the evergreen forests of North Karnataka and Goa.

The Indian giant flying squirrel was seen to occur in both evergreen and moist deciduous forests, while the Travancore flying squirrel was seen to occur only in evergreen forests. This was similar to the trend seen in the previous survey conducted in Kerala and Tamil Nadu (Rajamani 2001). The Travancore flying squirrel is possibly a habitat specialist confined to tropical moist evergreen forests.

When the habitat characteristics associated with the occurrence of flying squirrels were assessed, the maturity of the stand and the presence of large trees seemed to be important features required by the squirrels. An examination of the use of nest sites revealed that the age and size structure of the stand were important, and flying squirrels were seen to nest in mature stands. The density of trees in these stands was not significant, but the stands were largely comprised of trees of large girth.

The Travancore flying squirrel was seen in denser forests than was the Indian giant flying squirrel. Analyzing occurrence of the Indian giant flying squirrels across two different habitat types, the presence of mature stands with tall trees of large girth stood out in both forest types. In evergreen forests, flying squirrels were found in stands with higher canopy connectivity, and in moist deciduous forests, flying squirrels were seen to prefer stands with lower densities. This preference for stands of lower density is similar to preferences seen in the previous survey (Rajamani 2001) and could possibly be a reflection of its gliding habits. When several habitat variables were pooled for composite analysis the height and girth of trees in the stand were important to flying squirrel presence. Habitat disturbance is often a factor that affects populations of arboreal mammals (Weigl et al 1999), and some of the sites surveyed were heavily impacted by human disturbance. Logging and removal of trees for firewood purposes impact the forest structure, and affect stand density, basal area, canopy contiguity and the average stand height. Hunting is another pressure that was very much prevalent in certain parts of Karnataka. Of the two pressures (habitat deforestation and hunting), hunting seemed to have a greater impact on flying squirrel populations. While flying squirrels were still seen at sites with habitat disturbance, they were not sighted at places hunting was a common practice.

Immediate Conservation action required:

An issue of immediate conservation action is a stricter control of hunting and poaching activities in Karnataka, especially in reserve forests. The Travancore flying squirrel was sighted in Hamiyala, on the border of Pushpagiri WLS, in non-protected forest area. Balehalli RF is also non-protected forest, and efforts need to be made to integrate this site into a network of protected areas. The levels of hunting in these sites are high (from local records), and stricter night patrols are called for in many of the sites surveyed. A common method of hunting flying squirrels is using a gun and spotlight at night (results of this survey; Madhusudhan and Karanth 2002), and enforcing stricter night patrols would significantly reduce the threat levels to these species.

There exists a significant gap in the knowledge of flying squirrel ecology in the Oriental region (Lee and Liao 1998). Most intensive research on flying squirrels has been conducted in the Temperate regions, while basic knowledge of many species in the Oriental region is lacking. Though eleven species of flying squirrels are found in India, there has been little intensive research on them. The Oriental tropics have been singled out as a region with the highest number of threatened rodents (species and genera) (Amori and Gippoliti 2001). Intensive surveys and monitoring programs of the two species of flying squirrels are required to determine exact population densities, and long-term ecological field work is necessary to outline conservation plans for the two species in question in order to ensure their continued survival.

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APPENDIX**Table A1: Sampling effort in various sites.**

	<i>Site*</i>	<i>State</i>	<i>Protected / Non Protected area</i>	<i>Number of walks (n)</i>	<i>Distance sampled (km)</i>
1	Biligiri Rangaswami Temple WLS	Karnataka	PA	4	3.75
2	Nagarhole NP	Karnataka	PA	6	12.5
3	Brahmagiri WLS	Karnataka	PA	3	21.75
4	Talacaurvei WLS	Karnataka	PA	1	2
5	Pushpagiri WLS	Karnataka	PA	1	2.5
6	Kemmangundi RF	Karnataka	NPA	1	1.2
7	Bhadra WLS	Karnataka	PA	2	4
8	Kudremukh NP	Karnataka	PA	3	12
9	Someshwara WLS	Karnataka	PA	1	2
10	Balehalli RF	Karnataka	NPA	1	2.5
11	Agumbe RF	Karnataka	NPA	1	3
12	Mookambika WLS	Karnataka	PA	1	5.75
13	Sharavathy WLS	Karnataka	NPA	3	9
14	<i>Kans</i> around Sorab	Karnataka	NPA	2	4.5
15	Malemane	Karnataka	NPA	1	4
16	Yana	Karnataka	NPA	1	.6
17	Anshi NP	Karnataka	PA	3	6.3
18	Haliyal RF	Karnataka	NPA	1	2.3
19	Bhagwan Mahaveer NP	Goa	PA	2	8.2
20	Cotigaon WLS	Goa	PA	2	5.5
	TOTAL			40	113.35

* WLS- Wildlife Sanctuary, NP- National Park, RF – Reserve forests

Hunting and local knowledge of flying squirrels

Flying squirrels were reportedly hunted at various sites across the surveyed region. Most hunting was by local communities, either tribal or agricultural, and was largely for immediate consumption and not for sale in markets. Flying squirrels were not hunted much for medicinal value though certain communities (in BRT WLS) believe that the meat of flying squirrels has medicinal properties. This meat is given to cripples and people with asthma. The meat of flying squirrels is reported to be tastier than that of giant squirrels. The Indian Giant flying squirrel is the more commonly hunted of the two species of flying squirrels.

Table A2: Hunting of flying squirrels across different sites. Only sites where there was information was gathered are included in the following table, and sites where no information was gathered are excluded. This is not reflective of actual hunting patterns across sites but of time spent at sites and access to local communities.

<i>Site</i>	<i>Hunting</i>	<i>Method</i>	<i>Evidence</i>
Billigiri Rangaswamy Temple WLS	Yes	Traditional methods: - Climb tree, thrust stick into hollow, and get animal out during daytime - Climb tree, wrap cloth around hand and retrieve animal from hollow	Sambar found dead in ground trap < 2km from settlement. Reports from tribals of regular past hunting for flying squirrels, and reduced present hunting.
Nagarhole NP	No		Hunting in the past, but no current hunting
Brahmagiri WLS	Yes	Hunting at night with gun	Makutta – evidence of hunting - 6 gunshots during night transect
Kudremukh NP	Yes	Traditional methods: - noose outside nest on tree, - noose on fruiting tree	Mullodi – hunting common
Talacauveri WLS	Yes	Hunting at night with gun	Common palm civet found shot dead in rainforest patch Evidence of poaching, gunshots during transect, lights (reportedly poachers) moving in the valley from Kerala during night walk
Pushpagiri WLS	Yes	Hunting at night with gun	Hamilaya- hunting prevalent, “every family owns a gun”, shooting at night common
Someshwara WLS Agumbe	Yes Yes	Hunting at night with gun Hunting at night with gun	6 Gunshots during transect Sitanadi transect gunshots, evidence form local residents of hunting
Mookambika WLS	n/a		Reports of extensive past hunting

Local knowledge of flying squirrels was greater at sites where hunting was prevalent, and this was not restricted to tribal communities. Flying squirrels in most part of Karnataka were identified as *Harabeku*, and this term referred to the Indian giant flying squirrel in most cases. Certain regions had varying local names for the two species and these are listed below:

Table A3: Local names for flying squirrels

<i>Site</i>	<i>Travancore FS</i>	<i>Indian Giant FS</i>
Brahmagiri WLS	Iliparan, Umilipanjan	Harabeku, parabeku
Kudremukh NP	Umilipanjan (Tulu)	Malapanjan, panjan, (Tulu)
Pushpagiri WLS	Chitharalu	Haralubeku
Anshi NP		Phagmanjar
Goa: Bhagwan Mahaveer WLS, Cotigaon WLS		Pakhi/ pakhio

Local names for other species in the Anshi region bordering Goa:

Brown Palm Civet: Katendar

Slender loris: Vanmanush

Small Indian Civet: Javad

Giant squirrel: Shukru

Table A4: Other nocturnal mammals sighted during night transects

<i>Species</i>	<i>Site</i>	<i>Vegetation type</i>	<i>Number of individuals</i>
<i>Loris tardigradus</i> Slender loris	Kesave, Bhadra WLS	Moist deciduous forest	1
	Balehalli RF	Evergreen forest	3
	Megani valley RF	Evergreen forest	1
	Kanur, Sharavathi WLS	Evergreen forest	1
	Barpal, Anshi NP	Evergreen forest	2
	Makutta RF	Evergreen forest	1
	<i>Paradoxurus jerdonii</i> Brown palm civet	Arashinagudi falls, Mookambika WLS	Evergreen forest
Megani Valley		Evergreen forest	2
Barpal, Anshi NP		Evergreen forest	4
Doodsagar falls, Bhagwan Mahavir WLS		Evergreen forest	4
<i>Paradoxurus hermaphroditus</i> Common palm civet	Bhagwan Mahavir WLS	Moist deciduous forest	2
	Nagarhole NP	Moist deciduous forest	1
<i>Vivvericula indica</i> Small Indian Civet	Highway near Sirsi	Evergreen forest	1

* WLS- Wildlife Sanctuary, NP- National Park, RF – Reserve forests